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THE IMPACT OF INFORMATION-PSYCHOLOGICAL INFLUENCES AND CYBERBULLYING ON THE CONSCIOUSNESS OF MILITARY PERSONNEL

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ABSTRACT

The article investigates the problem of negative information-psychological impact on the consciousness of military personnel in the modern information society from a philosophical and theoretical perspective. Along with traditional manipulative methods, the phenomenon of cyberbullying is analyzed as the most dangerous form of encroachment on the spiritual and psychological sphere of the individual in the digital space. The mechanisms of the negative influence of information-psychological impacts on the consciousness of military personnel, as well as their social and professional stability, are revealed, and corresponding conclusions and recommendations are provided.

Keywords: information-psychological impact, cyberbullying, consciousness of military personnel, manipulation, disinformation, cognitive processes, emotional impact.

AXBOROT-PSIXOLOGIK TA'SIRLAR HAMDA KIBERZO'RAVONLIKNING HARBIY XIZMATCHILAR ONGIGA TA'SIRI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada zamonaviy axborot jamiyatida harbiy xizmatchilar ongiga salbiy axborot-psixologik ta'sirlar ko'rsatish muammosi falsafiy-nazariy jihatdan tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqotda an'anaviy manipulyativ usullar bilan bir qatorda, raqamli makonda shaxs ma'naviy-ruhiy olamiga tajovuz qilishning eng xavfli ko'rinishi bo'lgan kiberzo'ravonlik (kiberbulling) fenomeni tahlil qilingan. Axborot-psixologik ta'sirlarning harbiy xizmatchilar ongiga, ularning ijtimoiy va kasbiy barqarorligiga salbiy ta'sir etish mexanizmlari ochib berilgan hamda tegishli xulosa va takliflar berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: axborot-psixologik ta’sir, kiberzo‘ravonlik, harbiy xizmatchi ongi, manipulyatsiya, dezinformatsiya, kognitiv jarayonlar, emotsional ta’sir.

ВЛИЯНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЙ И КИБЕРБУЛЛИНГА НА СОЗНАНИЕ ВОЕННОСЛУЖАЩИХ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье с философско-теоретической точки зрения исследуется проблема негативного информационно-психологического воздействия на сознание военнослужащих в современном информационном обществе. Наряду с традиционными манипулятивными методами анализируется феномен киберзапугивания (кибербуллинга) как наиболее опасная форма посягательства на духовно-психологическую сферу личности в цифровом пространстве. Раскрываются механизмы негативного влияния информационно-психологических воздействий на сознание военнослужащих, их социальную и профессиональную стабильность, а также даются соответствующие выводы и предложения.

Ключевые слова: информационно-психологическое воздействие, киберзапугивание, сознание военнослужащих, манипуляция, дезинформация, когнитивные процессы, эмоциональное воздействие.

INTRODUCTION

In a modern society where information technologies are developing rapidly, information flows exert a powerful transforming influence on human consciousness and social relations. Therefore, information appears not only as a means of conveying information but also as a strategic socio-ideological resource that shapes human thinking, values, and social behavior. This situation requires a deep philosophical and socio-psychological analysis of the phenomenon of information-psychological influence. Today, these influences are not limited to the media or traditional propaganda, but are taking on new and more aggressive forms in the virtual space. In particular, cyberbullying, which is a modern form of encroachment on the spiritual and spiritual world of an individual through digital technologies, has become the most

dangerous local means of information and psychological influence. This situation manifests as an integral part of a destructive information-psychological attack aimed at undermining the morale and moral-psychological stability of military personnel through targeted discrimination, pressure, and discrediting in the virtual space.

Literature review on the topic. In this study, a complex of modern socio-philosophical and epistemological research methods was used to study the impact of information-psychological influences and the phenomenon of cyberviolence on the consciousness and social existence of military personnel. In particular, the dialectical approach and systematic analysis allowed for the study of information-psychological influences as a holistic destructive system, while the comparative-philosophical method served to compare the specific characteristics of cyberviolence in virtual space with traditional ideological attacks. The concept of information-psychological influence is a category formed at the intersection of several scientific directions: philosophy, sociology, psychology, and communication theory. The theoretical foundations of this category are linked to concepts explaining the openness of the human mind to the influence of information and the influence of social communication on human behavior.

Uzbek philosopher Professor M. Mamatrasulov notes: "Analyzing the impact of the information environment on the spiritual life of society, it should be noted that in the context of globalization, information has become an important factor in shaping human worldview and value systems" [1]. It is insufficient to understand information-psychological influence solely as a process of disseminating information. This phenomenon is primarily a socio-ideological mechanism aimed at influencing human consciousness, manifesting in connection with the content of information, the method of its presentation, and the psychology of the audience.

The phenomenon of information-psychological influence is explained by understanding the interdependence between information, psychology, and ideology. While information is a means of influencing human consciousness, psychology determines the process of its perception and processing, while ideology determines the semantic direction of this influence.

Uzbek scientist Professor E. Yusupov "Analyzes the impact of the information environment on human spirituality and shows the connection between information and ideology as an important factor for the development of society" [2]. In his opinion, ideological influences in the information space are capable of shaping a person's worldview and social position.

Accordingly, in the process of information-psychological influence, information serves not only as information but also as a signal carrying a specific ideological

meaning. Therefore, the analysis of the relationship between the content of information and its psychological perception is important in understanding this phenomenon.

In the modern information society, information has penetrated all spheres of human activity. The mass media, the Internet, and social networks play an important role in shaping human consciousness. This situation has turned information-psychological influence into an important factor in the life of society.

Uzbek researcher Professor A. Jalolov also notes that "the influence of information in the global information environment can affect the spiritual stability of society and national security"[3]. Information-psychological influence has become one of the primary factors shaping social relations and worldviews in modern society. Therefore, studying this phenomenon from a philosophical and social perspective is of great importance for ensuring the spiritual stability of society.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, emphasized that "ensuring spiritual security and protecting youth from various ideological influences is one of the important tasks of state policy" [4].

Uzbek philosopher Professor N. Kamilov notes that "national spirituality and cultural heritage are an important foundation for the stability of society, emphasizing the need to protect spiritual values in the global information environment"[5].

One of the most common methods of information-psychological influence is the mechanism of propaganda and manipulation. Propaganda is a form of information influence aimed at promoting a specific idea, viewpoint, or political position to a wide audience. Manipulation, on the other hand, manifests as a mechanism of psychological influence aimed at influencing the human mind in a latent way and turning the decision-making process in a specific direction.

Professor E. Yusupov, an Uzbek scholar, notes that "ideological influences in the information space are often carried out through manipulative methods, and the culture of critical information analysis is an important factor for the spiritual stability of society." [2; pp. 60-64.]. Accordingly, the primary goal of propaganda and manipulation methods is not to induce a person to consciously accept a specific idea, but to make it a natural and inevitable decision through psychological influence. Therefore, these methods should be evaluated not only as information technology but also as a mechanism of socio-ideological influence. Today, cyberbullying is emerging as a new and more aggressive virtual form of these manipulative mechanisms. While traditional propaganda is aimed at the public consciousness, cyberbullying is directed at a specific target-the military serviceman's personal digital space (social media profiles, personal data). Exerting virtual pressure on a serviceman through cyberbullying and humiliating them is an open and destructive form of the

aforementioned hidden manipulation, which serves to undermine an individual's self-confidence and alienate them from society.

Another important and dangerous method of information-psychological influence is the dissemination of disinformation and fake information. Disinformation is a strategy aimed at deliberately misleading the audience by spreading information that does not correspond to reality or is partially based on truth. Cyberbullying in the virtual space is often based on such disinformation and false accusations (fake news). Influencing human emotions plays a crucial role in the process of information-psychological influence. Methods of emotional impact are aimed at weakening the rational thinking of the audience and military personnel by evoking feelings of fear, anxiety, anger, or injustice. Cyberbullying also aims to destroy the emotional stability of a serviceman by artificially inducing a state of social fear, personal anxiety, and stress.

Uzbek philosopher Professor N. Komilov notes that "spiritual values influence a person's psychological stability, and influences based on emotions in the information environment can affect the spiritual stability of society" [5; pp.48-52].

In our view, the primary goal of emotional impact technologies is to distance a person from rational analysis. If a person perceives information based on emotions, they may lose the ability to critically analyze the content of the information.

In an informed society, human consciousness is formed in close connection with the information environment. Information is not only a means of conveying information but also manifests as a socio-psychological factor influencing human perception, thinking, feelings, and values. Therefore, when analyzing information-psychological influences, a comprehensive study of the mechanisms of influence on human consciousness from cognitive, emotional, and axiological perspectives is of great importance. These mechanisms influence how a person perceives reality, evaluates information, and shapes their worldview. The systemic nature of information-psychological influences is explained by the fact that they manifest simultaneously at the cognitive, emotional, and axiological levels. On the one hand, information influences a person's perception and thinking processes, while on the other hand, it can also influence their emotional state and value system. Therefore, information-psychological influences manifest as a multi-stage socio-psychological mechanism that serves to form certain ideas, views, and attitudes in the human mind.

One of the main mechanisms of information-psychological influence is associated with cognitive processes-human perception, memory, and thinking activity. Cognitive mechanisms manifest during the process of human information reception and processing. Information can shape certain meanings and ideas in the human mind and change one's views on reality.

Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget "emphasized that human thinking and cognitive processes are formed under the influence of external information, and showed that cognitive development occurs as a result of human interaction with the environment"[6]. This view is important for understanding the mechanisms of information-psychological influence.

In our view, the cognitive mechanism of information-psychological influence is manifested through the gradual change of a person's perceptions of reality. If a person is constantly in a certain information environment, their way of perceiving reality can also adapt to this information environment.

Influence on human emotions plays an important role in the process of information-psychological influence. Emotional influence can influence a person's decision-making process by triggering emotions such as fear, anger, injustice, or anxiety.

Uzbek philosopher Professor N. Komilov notes that "emotions and a system of values play an important role in the spiritual stability of a person, noting that emotional influences in the information environment can affect human spirituality" [5; pp. 53-56.].

In our view, the mechanisms of emotional influence can temporarily weaken a person's ability to think rationally. If information has a strong impact on a person's emotions, they may be deprived of the opportunity to critically analyze the content of the information.

Information-psychological influence can also affect a person's system of values and beliefs. Values are considered an important factor that determines a person's social behavior and worldview. Ideas disseminated in the information environment can influence a person's value system and change their social position.

The Uzbek philosopher, Professor M. Mamatrasulov, emphasizes that "national values are the fundamental foundation of the spiritual stability of society, and the protection of values in the global information environment is of great importance" [1; pp. 81-85.].

In our view, one of the most important aspects of information-psychological influence is its influence on a person's value system. Because a person's worldview and social position largely depend on their values.

The final result of information-psychological influence can be associated with a change in a person's worldview. Worldview is considered an important spiritual category that defines a person's attitude toward social reality.

Professor E. Yusupov, an Uzbek scholar, notes that "a person's worldview is formed under the influence of the information environment and spiritual values in society, and the process of worldview transformation is intensifying in the global

information environment." [2; pp. 64-68]. In our view, the information environment can influence a person's social position by gradually changing their worldview. Therefore, an in-depth study of the process of worldview transformation is of great importance when analyzing information-psychological influences.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Military personnel are a social group that performs a special social function in society and carries out activities directly related to state security. Therefore, their consciousness, values, and social relations are determined not only by their personal worldview but also by socio-ethical principles such as service discipline, military duty, and loyalty to the state. In this environment, information-psychological influences manifest in a unique way compared to other social groups. These influences can affect the consciousness, teamwork, and service motivation of military personnel.

The consciousness of military personnel is shaped differently from ordinary social roles in civil society. Military service requires discipline, responsibility, and a readiness for collective action. Therefore, military consciousness is based on individual views as well as collective values. That is, the serviceman realizes himself not only as an individual, but also as part of a specific collective and state system. Therefore, when information-psychological influences affect this system of consciousness, they can also spread through collective relations.

The moral foundation of military service consists of values such as duty, oath, and loyalty to the state. These values signify a social responsibility that transcends the personal interests of the serviceman. Therefore, information-psychological influences can influence this value system.

In our view, one of the most important directions of information-psychological influence may be aimed at changing the attitude of military personnel toward the concepts of duty and loyalty. If the information environment presents these values as relative or secondary, this may also affect service motivation. In the military community, information influence is usually transmitted through collective communication and interaction. In a collective setting, information can spread quickly and be discussed among employees. In our view, information influence in the military community is often transmitted through trust relations. If certain information is perceived as a reliable source among employees, it can spread quickly within the team and influence general opinion.

Ideological influences in the information space are considered a complex socio-psychological process that can influence the consciousness of members of society, especially military personnel. Therefore, technical or administrative measures alone are not enough to counter information-psychological influences. Resilience to such influences relies on a person's intellectual, spiritual, and social resources. Critical

thinking, information literacy, a system of national and military values, collective unity, and mechanisms for forming ideological immunity are of particular importance as the primary factors ensuring ideological stability.

Critical thinking is considered a human intellectual defense mechanism in resisting information-psychological influences. Critical thinking allows a person to analyze information, evaluate its source, and verify its authenticity. This process helps to form a stable position in relation to various manipulative influences in the information environment.

Critical thinking is a vital intellectual resource that protects human consciousness in the information environment. If a person has the ability to analyze information and evaluate its source, they can maintain a stable position against various ideological influences.

In the analysis of information-psychological influences, it is crucial to identify the sensitive points of the military personnel's consciousness. These points can be related to a person's emotional state, social relations, and value system. Sensitive points in the minds of military personnel can be associated with the following factors: service conditions and social environment, attitudes toward justice and trust, collective relations, and leadership factors. Therefore, it is important to take these factors into account when analyzing information-psychological influences.

The system of national and military values plays an important role in ensuring ideological stability. National values define a person's cultural and spiritual identity, while military values shape principles such as duty, loyalty, and responsibility.

Uzbek philosopher Professor N. Komilov emphasizes that "national spirituality is an important foundation for the stability of society, and national values play an important role in the formation of a person's spiritual immunity" [5; pp. 60-63.]. For military personnel, the value system is not merely a moral concept, but the moral foundation of service activities. If military personnel are firmly formed in values such as duty, loyalty, and collectivism, they will be resistant to various ideological influences in the information environment.

In a military environment, collective unity and mutual trust are considered essential social factors for ideological stability. In a collective environment, trust and solidarity among employees play a crucial role in resisting information influences. When there is an atmosphere of trust in the military community, service members are critical of various manipulative influences spreading in the information environment. Because in a collective environment, information is often evaluated through mutual discussion and debate.

The concept of ideological immunity is of great importance in ensuring resilience against information and psychological influences. Ideological immunity

represents a person's critical and stable attitude toward various ideas and influences in the information environment.

Ideological immunity refers to an individual's ability to maintain an independent position regarding various ideas and influences within the information environment. If a person has developed critical thinking, loyalty to national values, and a sense of collective responsibility, they will be resilient to various ideological influences in the information environment.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In general, information-psychological influences are one of the complex socio-transformational processes in the modern information space, which have the ability to exert a transboundary influence on human consciousness, worldview, and the value system. This situation poses a serious threat, especially for military personnel—a strategically important social group that ensures the spiritual and ideological security of society. Today, cyberbullying is emerging as the most aggressive and individualized tool of these destructive influences. It is aimed at undermining the mental stability of a serviceman by encroaching on their privacy in a virtual space. Therefore, the philosophical and theoretical analysis of such ideological influences and forms of digital violence in the information environment, as well as the identification of their mechanisms of influence on military consciousness, is one of the priority areas for ensuring national security. Taking this into account, we recommend the following.

Formation of axiological immunity: Creating an internal system of philosophical-critical observation and value-based protection against cyberviolence in the minds of military personnel;

Development of epistemological criteria: Systematization of cognitive methods that clearly distinguish between virtual reality (simulation) and real social reality in the minds of military personnel;

Formation of virtual ethical norms: Conceptual organization of the fight against psychological attacks in the digital space based on the "freedom and responsibility" categories of social philosophy.

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